

An Intelligent System for Human Intent and Environment Detection Through Tactile Data^{*}

Gianluca Laudante and Salvatore Pirozzi

Università degli Studi della Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”, Aversa (CE), Italy
gianluca.laudante@unicampania.it

Abstract. The tackled application aims at demonstrating the effectiveness of using tactile sensors for multiple purposes at the same time. In particular, tactile data are exploited for: the estimation of a wire diameter by using a previously trained classifier; teaching the robot new wire routing trajectories in case of unknown grasped wires; stopping the autonomous execution of previously learned trajectories to avoid damages due to possible wire entanglements.

Keywords: Tactile Sensors, Wire Manipulation, Intelligent System.

1 Introduction

Tactile sensors represent a key enabling technology to improve the robot capabilities in the execution of complex tasks. For example, grasping and manipulation tasks can be successfully executed only by knowing specific geometrical and physical features of the objects, together with an estimation of interaction forces/torques between the robotic system and the environment. In recent applications, the robotic systems are also often used to implement safe and efficient physical Human Robot Interaction tasks, which requires the knowledge of interaction forces and contact locations in order to perform cooperation and co-manipulation tasks and to limit damage from accidental impacts. To this aim the robots are more and more frequently equipped with sensorized grippers, capable to reproduce an artificial sense of touch, trying to imitate humans, which can perform complex tasks thanks to their sophisticated tactile perception [1, 2].

Recently, many researchers started to present results about touch sensing solutions applied to daily life applications, based on both model based and machine learning approaches. In [3], authors present an application to distinguish materials on the basis of friction, by using a Naive Bayes classifier. Bandyopadhyaya et al. [4] uses a piezoresistive tactile sensor to distinguish objects of different softness using Decision Tree and Naive Bayes methods. In [5], authors presented a solution for the discrimination of object curvature using a sparse tactile sensor array. Da Fonseca et al. [6] proposed a combination of machine learning methods and fuzzy logic controllers to improve the grasp stability through tactile data

^{*} This work was partially supported by the European Commission within the H2020 REMODEL Project (no. 870133)

for an under-actuated hand. An interesting feature of tactile sensors is that they can be used not only for recognition and classification strategies as discussed above, but also for control purposes, such as grasping and manipulation [7–10]. The interested reader can deepen the topic of tactile sensing for dexterous manipulation by referring to the review papers [11, 12], and references therein. As detailed in the following, in this paper the tactile sensor will be exploited also as teaching system, as alternative approach to commonly used solutions [13, 14].

The main objective of this paper is to demonstrate that the tactile sensor, developed by the authors and detailed in [15], can be used to tackle complex tasks by combining machine learning and model based methods applied to the same tactile data. In previous papers, the authors demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed technology for the shape recognition of grasped wires during manipulation tasks devoted to the switchgear assembly [16] and a solution for the classification of wires on the basis of their diameters [17]. In this work, past and new methods are combined in a more articulated solution, where teaching phases and task execution phases are automatically managed on the basis of object classification. During the teaching phases an human operator interacts with the robotic system by exploiting the tactile data as guidance system, while during the execution phases the tactile data are used to avoid damages in case of unintended environmental interactions. A classification method trained on the basis of tactile data supervises if the grasped object needs a teaching phase or can be directly used for an execution task. In the next sections the tackled task is detailed together with the proposed approach. Finally experiments are reported to demonstrate the effectiveness of the implemented solution.

2 Interaction Task

As discussed, the objective is to demonstrate how it is possible to exploit the same sensor to execute a complex task. To this aim, a single tactile sensor is used to accomplish different phases in an example application: routing a wire following a certain path depending on the diameter of the wire.

The whole task is resumed in the flowchart in Fig. 1(a). Initially, the robot moves to a fixed starting position to grasp a wire. Then, an estimation of the wire diameter is obtained and it is used to search for a trajectory in a database. In case there is no saved trajectory, an operator, by pulling the wire, teaches the robot the path to follow the next time a wire with the same diameter is grasped. Instead, if a trajectory already exists, the robot executes the wire routing as it has been taught and stops the motion in case a force on the wire is detected, which could be due, for example, to an entanglement during the trajectory execution. During the task, the tactile sensor is used for three different purposes:

1. Estimate the diameter of the wire;
2. Compute the command for moving the robot during the teaching phase;
3. Stop the robot if the wire gets entangled during the autonomous routing.

Fig. 1. Task flowchart (a) and hardware setup: robot, gripper and fingers (b).

2.1 Task Robotic System

The robotic system consists of an Universal Robot UR5e manipulator equipped with a Robotiq Hand-E gripper that has a couple of custom designed fingers: an active finger equipped with a tactile sensor and a passive one (see Fig. 1(b)).

Tactile Sensor The active finger integrates the tactile sensor detailed in [15]: it consists of 25 photo-reflectors integrated into a standard Printed Circuit Boards (PCB) and suitably assembled with a deformable pad made of silicone. The optoelectronic devices are organized in a 5×5 matrix, with a spatial resolution equal to 3.55 mm and a sensitive area of about $21 \times 21 \text{ mm}^2$. The photo-reflectors are constituted by infrared LEDs and photo-transistors optically matched. The LEDs are driven by adjustable current sources and the photo-transistors signals are acquired by a microcontroller equipped with 25 low-noise A/D channels with a 12-bit resolution. The silicone pad transduces the external contacts into deformations measured in a discrete number of points by the optical devices. The measurements correspond to the voltages available on the photo-transistors on the basis of light emitted by LEDs and reflected by the bottom side of the deformable pad. Table 1 reports the main features of the sensor, but the interested reader can find additional details in [15]. The passive finger is equipped with the same deformable pad as the active one, but without the optoelectronic components. Figure 2(a) reports a detail of the fingers mounted on the gripper.

Table 1. Main features of the active finger.

Taxels Number	Sensing Area	Spatial Resolution	Sampling Frequency	Response Time
25 (5×5)	$21 \times 21 \text{ mm}^2$	3.55 mm	500 Hz	< 0.01 s

Fig. 2. Active/Passive fingers couple (a) and taxel matrix of the tactile sensor (b).

A suitable ROS (Robot Operating System) node has been developed to make the tactile data available from the microcontroller. Initially, the node acquires the voltage offsets from all photo-transistors when the sensor is in rest condition. These offsets are the mean value of the first 50 received voltage samples. Then, in normal working conditions, the node makes available, at a frequency of 500 Hz, the tactile map corresponding to acquired voltages cleared from initial offsets, denoted as v_{rc} in the following. Also details about the software can be found in [15]. Figure 2(b) shows the taxel distribution in the 5×5 matrix and the sensor frame positioned in the center of the sensing area, by highlighting for each taxel the corresponding voltage signal v_{rc} , defined by exploiting its row and column indices within the matrix.

2.2 Task Program Architecture

The complete program architecture for the proposed task, represented with a block scheme in Fig. 3, is developed using ROS¹, an open-source software framework for robotic applications. Each block in the scheme is detailed in the following.

Diameter Classifier An estimation of the diameter of the grasped wire is needed for the task execution. This is achieved by a suitably trained classifier based on a machine learning algorithm, detailed in a previous paper [17] by

¹ <https://www.ros.org/>

Fig. 3. Block scheme of the program architecture.

the authors. To resume, the diameter is estimated by a classifier, consisting in a feedforward neural network, able to recognize 6 different diameters (i.e., [1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4] mm). The inputs to the neural network are 26 values, i.e., the 25 voltage signals v_{rc} of the tactile sensor and the relative distance between the gripper fingers. The node implements a ROS service² that returns the estimated diameter of the currently grasped wire.

Interaction Indicators The 25 tactile signals are also used for the computation of three indicators, required by other components of the program. These indicators are all based on a comparison between the current tactile map, i.e., at time t , and the tactile map right after the initial grasp, i.e., at time t_0 . The first indicator is the sum of the absolute values of the variations in the tactile map:

$$i_{stop} = \sum_{c=1}^5 \sum_{r=1}^5 (|v_{rc}(t)| - |v_{rc}(t_0)|) \quad (1)$$

This is a generic indicator to detect an interaction with the environment. The other two indicators are used to move the robot according to the force exerted by the operator on the grasped wire during the teach phase. In particular, one is used for the translation velocity of the end effector and the other for the rotational one, since the first is related to a shear force and the second to a rotational torque. Starting from the first indicator, it is computed as:

$$i_{transl} = \sum_{c=1}^3 \left(\sum_{r=1}^5 (v_{rc}(t) - v_{rc}(t_0)) \right) + \sum_{c=3}^5 \left(\sum_{r=1}^5 (v_{rc}(t) - v_{rc}(t_0)) \right) \quad (2)$$

that is the sum of the total variation in the left part of the sensor, i.e., columns ‘ c ’ from 1 to 3, and the total variation in the right part, i.e., columns from 3 to

² <http://wiki.ros.org/Services>

5. The choice for this indicator comes from how the tactile signals respond to shear forces applied in the x direction of the sensor frame (see Fig. 2(b)), due to the asymmetry of the optoelectronic components. In fact, when a force is applied in the positive x direction the tactile signals increase, while they decrease when the force is applied in the opposite direction. Since the sign of all the variations is the same, the total variations of the left and right parts are summed. The second indicator is similar to the first one and it is computed as:

$$i_{rot} = \sum_{c=1}^3 \left(\sum_{r=1}^5 (v_{rc}(t) - v_{rc}(t_0)) \right) - \sum_{c=3}^5 \left(\sum_{r=1}^5 (v_{rc}(t) - v_{rc}(t_0)) \right) \quad (3)$$

In this case the total variations of the left and right parts of the sensor are subtracted rather than summed. The choice of this indicator directly derives from the observation of how an operator would act on the grasped wire so to rotate the robot end effector. The most intuitive action is to pull the portion of the grasped wire protruding out one side of the sensor while pushing the one on the other side. As a consequence, this leads to opposite variations in the two sides of tactile sensor, i.e., positive in the “pushed” side and negative in the “pulled” one. Since in this case the variations have different signs, the total variations of the left and right parts are subtracted.

Execute Trajectory This component deals with the autonomous routing of a wire on the basis of a previously taught trajectory and for point to point motion of the robot end effector. It is a ROS action server³ that accepts a trajectory as a goal and returns a boolean value and a trajectory as result. The latter is important when the routing execution is halted after the detection of an external force applied on the wire, i.e., the i_{stop} indicator exceeding a fixed threshold. In this case, in fact, the node indicates that the task has not been completed and returns the portion of the trajectory not yet executed. In this way, an operator can choose to continue the task from the current position or to abort it.

Hand Guidance This component transforms the interactions of the operator with the grasped wire in robot movements (in the 2D plane). This node, in fact, converts the indicators in Eqs. (2) and (3) in velocity commands for the robot. In particular, the conversion consists in applying a saturated dead-zone function, as the one in Fig. 4, to the indicators. It is useful to regularize the robot behaviour during the teaching when the indicators oscillate around zero, to limit the robot maximum velocity and to increase/decrease the sensibility of the robot velocity to the operator actions by changing the slope in the dead-zone function. The node is implemented as a ROS action server accepting, as a goal, a target position and a timeout value. The returned result is a boolean value equal to *true* if the target position has been reached before the timeout, and *false* otherwise. Fig. 5 shows two sequences representing the operator guiding the robot in both translations (Fig. 5(a)) and rotations (Fig. 5(b)) movements.

³ <http://wiki.ros.org/actionlib>

Fig. 4. Saturated dead-zone function.

Fig. 5. Operator guiding the robot in a translation (a) and in a rotation (b).

Trajectory Recorder While the operator is guiding the robot, the executed trajectory needs to be “learnt” by the robot in order to be then reproduced. This is in charge of the *Trajectory Recorder* node, that is implemented as a ROS node offering two services: one to start the recording and one to stop it. The latter accepts a boolean flag to choose whether the recorded trajectory must be saved or not.

Master Node This represents the “task executor”, i.e., the component that controls all the operations. It starts the tasks by sending a two-points trajectory to the *Execute Trajectory* action server, in order to move the robot in a fixed start

pose. Once the end effector is in the desired pose, the gripper fingers are periodically closed until a contact is detected and the node asks the *Diameter Classifier* for the estimated diameter. Hence, knowing the diameter, the existence of the corresponding trajectory is checked. In case the trajectory does not exist, the node starts the recording by calling the corresponding service of the *Trajectory Recorder* node and sends a goal to the *Hand Guidance* action server. Once the teaching operation has been completed (or the timeout has been reached), the *Master Node* stops the recording asking the responsible component to save the trajectory (or discard it in case of timeout). Instead, if the trajectory already exists, it is loaded from the database, scaled in velocity if requested, and sent to the *Execute Trajectory* action server. In both cases, once the trajectory has been completed, the node opens the gripper fingers and commands the robot to reach a fixed final pose. Finally, the operator is asked if there is another wire to be routed and, in case, the procedure re-starts.

3 Experimental Results

This section reports an example test for showing the functionality of all the components in the program detailed above. The task consists in routing five electrical wires, with two having a diameter of 2.0 mm, two with a diameter of 2.5 mm and the last one with a diameter of 4.0 mm.

At the beginning of the task no trajectory is in the database, so the operator teaches the robot the desired trajectories. The teaching phases are reported in Fig. 6, where the translational and rotational velocity commands derived from the tactile indicators are reported in blue, and the robot end effector pose in terms of x^b coordinate and angle θ_z^b about z axis w.r.t. the base of the robot are reported in red. After the teaching for each wire, the robot executes autonomously the routing for the remaining two wires following the correct trajectories. The pose of the robot during the autonomous routing is reported in the top graphs in Fig. 7, where the red line is the x^b coordinate of the end effector and the dashed blue line is the angle θ_z^b . In these graphs there are time intervals (i.e., [149, 154] s, [183, 187] s, [192, 196] s) during which the robot keeps the position. These intervals start in correspondence of peaks in the indicator i_{stop} reported in the bottom graphs of Fig. 7 and result from the operator pulling the wire during the trajectory execution, simulating an entanglement. The threshold for this test has been set to 0.12 V in order to be at least one order of magnitude above the sensor noise and to avoid that the weight of the wire itself is detected as a contact, stopping the execution. This value is tunable depending on the application and it can be reduced (taking into account the sensor noise) or increased to make the robot more or less sensible, respectively.

4 Conclusions and Future Works

The paper showed how a single tactile sensor can be exploited for different tasks in a complex application. In the proposed example, the same sensor has been

used to estimate the diameter of an electrical wire, to teach the robot a trajectory using a lead-through programming approach and to detect forces acting on the routed wire during the autonomous execution in order to stop the task. A current limitation of the presented application is the possibility of moving the

Fig. 6. Commanded robot velocities and end effector pose (x^b and θ_z^b) during the teach phase for wires with diameter of 2.0, 2.5 and 4.0 mm from left to right, respectively.

Fig. 7. End effector pose (x^b and θ_z^b) and indicator i_{stop} during the autonomous routing for wires with diameter of 2.5 and 2.0 mm from left to right, respectively.

robot on a 2D plane only. Hence, as a future direction, a couple of sensorized fingers will be used to extract new tactile-based indicators in order to achieve the possibility of motion in the 3D space.

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